

Prediction of Packing Density of Multi-Sized Aggregates using Grading Models and Compressible Packing Model

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ABSTRACT

The packing density and stability of the aggregate mixtures significantly affect the quality of concrete, particularly in infrastructural applications. The Carneiro and Dinger-Funk (D-F) models are two of the tools utilized in the generation of aggregate grading for concrete applications. For the first time, this study aimed to develop a methodology for the determination of the Carneiro distribution modulus (P_r) and the D-F distribution modulus (q) for a given aggregate system that provides optimal packing characteristics considering the packing density and segregation potential. In this study, combinations of two coarse aggregate classes (19 to 4.75 mm and 9.5 to 2.36 mm) and two fine aggregates (4.75 to 0.15 mm and 600 to 75 μm) were generated using a number of trial values of P_r and q . The packing density and segregation potential of each aggregate mixture were then computed using the compressible packing model, considering equivalent idealized spherical aggregate particles. For the aggregates considered in this study, results indicated that the optimal mixtures result in the range $0.85 \leq P_r \leq 0.90$ and $0.15 \leq q \leq 0.25$ for Carneiro and D-F models, respectively. Although both models appear to produce equivalent aggregate mixture characteristics, the D-F model is less responsive to changes in the distribution modulus. Hence, it is more flexible for obtaining an aggregate mixture composition with optimal packing characteristics.

Keywords: Concrete, Aggregate, Compressible Packing Model, Packing density, Segregation potential, Carneiro model, Dinger-Funk model.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Aggregates are one of the most often utilized materials in civil engineering applications, accounting for the lion's share of the weight or volume of the concrete mixture used in buildings and pavements. For different purposes, unique combinations of aggregate sizes are combined, resulting in varied densities, a factor that has been demonstrated to impact the hardened quality of concrete and the performance of granular aggregate mixtures in desired applications. As a result, concrete practitioners are concerned about the packing density and strength of the aggregate mixtures. As a composite material, concrete comprises four primary components: cement, aggregates (fine and coarse) and water. Fine and coarse aggregates account for approximately 60 to 80 percent of the total volume of concrete [1]. The compositional quantity that can be crammed into a given volume is referred to as the packing density. The packing density, which is a physical characteristic of aggregates, has a crucial influence on all properties of concrete. Other influencing physical characteristics include roughness or texture, quantity of fine aggregate, shape and quantity of flaky or angular particles present in the concrete volume [1].

The packing density of the concrete depends largely on the shape of the aggregate particles. The particles are either spherical or non-spherical in shape, with the latter having increased analytical and modeling complexities owing to more associated parameters (shape, orientation, and size). Physically, non-spherical particles have been found to have higher packing densities than spherical particles [2]. Owing to the ease of movement, the packing density of the components primarily influences the behavior of fresh concrete, where a higher aggregate packing degree leads to a reduction in the amount of cement required for a volume of concrete [3–5]. Aside from the economic gain that comes with reducing cement quantity, higher aggregates have an indirect environmental benefit by minimizing the use of scarce resources, thereby lowering anthropogenic emissions. Approximately 5% of global anthropogenic CO₂ emissions are contributed by the cement industry, making aggregate packing one of the vital CO₂-emission strategies [5,6].

In modern concrete mixture design, the packing density continues to play a vital role because of the increased awareness that its maximization through aggregate and cementitious material grading adjustments can improve the overall performance of the concrete mixture [7]. For example, the use of recycled aggregate (RA) to partially or totally replace natural aggregate (NA) in concrete has been recognized as important green construction practice. However, RA

concrete tends to exhibit inferior qualities, unless specific treatments are given. One of such treatments is particle packing optimization of RA-NA blends [8]. By optimizing the RA packing to improve the mechanical properties of RA concrete paving blocks, Chu et al. [9] recently demonstrated that the performance of RA concrete could approach that of NA concrete. In their study, a strength increase in excess of 150% was obtained using optimized aggregate packing. Elsewhere, the compressive strength of concrete was shown to exhibit positive linear correlation to the degree of packing of paste and aggregate phases of concrete [4,5,9]. Therefore, the application of packing optimization of concrete phases is central to the attainment of sustainable use of concrete and similar construction materials.

For an aggregate combination, the packing density (ϕ) represents the degree of compactness of the aggregate mixture. Various models have been employed to theoretically calculate ϕ . One of these is the compressible packing model (CPM), which has been shown to provide sufficient accuracy in the calculation of packing density by incorporating three important parameters that affect the packing of aggregates: the size, shape, and compaction method. CPM is superior to other models owing to its theoretical applicability to multi-sized mixtures compared to other binaries-only models [10]. Carneiro and Dinger-Funk (D-F) models are another two important tools for proportioning aggregate-size combinations in concrete applications. For a given aggregate mix, the two-parameter Carneiro model employs a constant progression ratio (P_r) for a specified number of sieves (N) to produce a well-graded aggregate combination [11]. The three-parameter D-F packing model is another tool that can be used to generate a graded aggregate distribution [12] given a prescribed distribution modulus q and the maximum and minimum sizes of the aggregate particles to produce a well-graded aggregate combination [13]. However, there seems to be no explicit information in the literature regarding the value of P_r or q in the respective model that produces the densest particle distribution or the implications of changes in the values of these model parameters on the segregation characteristics of a given system of aggregates.

In this study, the Carneiro and D-F models were utilized to generate graded distributions from a combination of four grades of aggregates, which were then subjected to the determination of packing densities and segregation potential using CPM to obtain the optimal ranges of P_r and q considering the packing density and segregation potential. The computational results were analyzed and discussed, leading to important insights on aggregate packing and compositional characteristics in relation particle distribution moduli for the grading models considered.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

This section explores and reviews the compressive packing model (CPM), Carneiro model, and Dinger-Funk (D-F) model in terms of size combinations considered, types of aggregate used, and the procedures and standards adopted in experiments and packing density calculations.

2.1 Studies on the Compressible Packing Model

Many studies have investigated CPM using various types of aggregates and experimental procedures. Yuan et al. [14] conducted an experiment using the Chinese standard JTG E20-2011 on binary and ternary combinations of crushed diorite (as a coarse aggregate) and limestone filler (as a fine aggregate) for large-stone porous asphalt mixtures. Considering their experimental values, they found that the accuracy of the CPM for the calculation of packing density decreased with an increasing number of aggregate classes. Thus, statistical correction factors were proposed to minimize the differences between the experimental and CPM values.

Baghaee and Baaj conducted an experiment [15] following French standards on five different classes of aggregates collected from northern Ontario, Canada. Using *Solver add-in* in Microsoft Excel, they found that the degree of packing and strength of the combination depended on the type, shape, and number of aggregate classes in the combination. More importantly, CPM optimization helped to obtain precise blending ratios that led to the highest packing degree. Similar findings were reported by Kwan and Chan [16], and Soliman and Tagnit-Hamou [17]. In a separate study, Arora et al. [18] tested combinations of five classes of fine and coarse aggregates, conforming to ASTM C33 [19], using MATLAB to generate 885 combinations. They found that the ideal combination was 60% coarse and 40% fine aggregates. Similar findings were reported by Hettiarachchi and Mampearachchi [20] and Sebaibi et al. [21] using binary mixtures.

Putten et al. [22] used basalt and porphyry as crushed aggregate class 2/4 and fine quartz sand as rounded aggregate class 0.25/0.5, following the experimental method adopted by de Larrard [10]. They found that the error in the round-round and round-crushed blends was very low, and that the CPM reasonably predicted the highest packing density for these cases.

Bala et al. [23] carried out experimental work on 0-4 mm sand and two types of gravel (4-10 mm and 10-20 mm) collected from three different French quarries, following the European standards NF EN 1097-6 and NF EN 933-1 for the mechanical and geometrical characterization of aggregates, respectively. They found that the accuracy of the CPM was

higher for round aggregate mixtures than for crushed aggregates. Furthermore, the accuracy of CPM increased with an increase in the size ratio of the elementary classes. In addition, they found that the back-calculated K value may vary from one mixture to another, particularly for crushed aggregates. They opined that CPM is reasonably applicable to large granular sizes without the need to create sub-sizes.

2.2 Studies on the Carneiro Model

The Carneiro model is a straightforward aggregate packing model used to generate a graded particle size distribution that obeys geometric progression. It has been proposed for use in aggregate proportioning for concrete applications [24]. Research papers have been published on the application of the Carneiro model for mixture proportioning of self-compacting concrete. These application cases successfully proved the strength of the Carneiro model for this type of concrete compared to other models, such as the Andreasen model [11,25].

2.3 Studies on the Dinger-Funk Model

The Dinger-Funk (D-F) model is a popular packing model used to generate well-graded aggregate distributions using continuously graded particulate systems [26]. This model has been successfully applied in several concrete applications. Researchers have studied the behavior of aggregate combinations corresponding to different values of q , the D-F distribution modulus. Hunger [27] found that a high distribution modulus ($q > 0.5$) leads to coarser aggregate mixes, whereas lower values ($q < 0.25$) lead to mixes that are richer in fines. Brouwers [28] suggested that a value of q ranging between 0 and 0.28 would result in optimum packing for various aggregate applications.

Numerous studies have been conducted on the D-F model involving different concrete mixture design applications, successfully proving the strength of the D-F model in designing aggregate combinations for normal-density [26], lightweight [29], and ultra-high-performance concrete (UHPC) [30].

3 RESEARCH SIGNIFICANCE

Prior to the recent times, the design of concrete mixtures was largely governed by prescriptive requirements. However, the recent technology and environmental landscape calls for performance-based engineering of construction materials, especially concrete, being the primary construction material. Thus, more emphasis should be placed on the fundamentals of

sustainable design, part of which is the optimization of packing characteristics of concrete phases. Many studies on packing optimization involves the generation of large number of random combination ratios of aggregate size classes within which the optimal packing density is searched, raising computational costs. While these studies mostly focus on packing density as the sole objective, concrete applications also require stable particulate system with minimum segregation potential. The current study fits into the context by offering a new and comprehensive approach for the determination of optimal aggregate blending ratios and insights into the packing characteristics of concrete aggregates through the synergistic use of industry-standard grading models and a robust packing model, CPM. This paper provides an easy-to-follow procedure along with a reference to the published version of the developed computer code to implement the approach presented in the paper.

4 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Materials

In this study, four aggregate classes were utilized, two of which were classified as coarse aggregates, and the remaining two were fine aggregates conforming to ASTM C33 [19]. The coarse aggregate was limestone obtained from a quarry in the eastern province of Saudi Arabia. The particle size distributions (PSDs) of the aggregates are shown in Figure 1. Notably, these aggregates were not utilized for physical experimentation; however, their PSD characteristics were employed in the packing density and mixture stability computations conducted in this study.

Figure 1: PSDs of the four aggregates utilized.

4.2 Methodology

As stated earlier, this study aimed to contribute to the methodology for obtaining aggregate mixtures with optimum packing density from a given set of aggregate size classes. The utilization of the CPM to obtain the packing density of an aggregate system relies on several input parameters. These parameters include the array $\{\varphi_i\}$ of the actual packing densities of the individual fractions of mean sizes $\{d_i\}$ included in the calculation scheme. For a given aggregate system, φ_i is typically obtained through experimental laboratory measurements. However, this study used the calculated values of φ_i for equivalent spherical particles using the Yamada and Miyauchi (Y-M) model. Although the experimental values of φ_i are generally expected to be different from the corresponding model values, this study proposes that the model values are correlated with the experimental values, and hence, are useful for the objectives of the present work.

As for the generation of the trial aggregate combinations that are submitted to the CPM calculations, two different grading models were utilized, as stated earlier, to conduct a comparative assessment of the models for the purpose as well as to establish the respective distribution modulus ranges, resulting in optimum packing of aggregate particles considering packing density and mixture stability or segregation potential.

4.3 Mathematical Models and Preliminary Analyses

Starting from the PSDs of the aggregates used in this study, as presented in Figure 1, the Carneiro and D-F models were employed to generate various trial aggregate distributions based on nine sieve openings and varying distribution moduli in the respective model cases. Through CPM computations, the packing density and segregation potential of each trial aggregate distribution were determined, taking the actual packing density of the individual mean size fractions as those given by the Yamada and Miyauchi (Y-M) model [31]. Although the Carneiro, D-F, and CPM models are discussed in Section 2 in the context of general literature information, the mathematics of these models along with the Y-M model are described in the following subsections considering technical application details.

4.3.1 The Carneiro model

The Carneiro model [20] is a two-parameter model used to generate a well-graded aggregate mixture for concrete applications. It is based on the idea of a constant ratio of the percentage of aggregates retained between two consecutive sieves. The model is based on:

$$P_1 = \frac{100(1 - P_r)}{1 - P_r^N} \% \quad (1)$$

where P_1 = first term of the geometric progression

P_r = Carneiro distribution modulus, constant ratio of the mass of particles retained between a pair of sieves.

N = number of sieve intervals = (number of sieves – 1).

Using equation (1), the first term of the geometric progression (percentage retained between the first two largest sieve sizes), the percentage of aggregates retained on the next lower sieve size, was calculated by multiplying P_1 by a chosen value of P_r . The subsequent percentages were calculated in a similar manner, leading to the percentage retained on a sieve size i given by the geometric series:

$$P_i = \frac{100(1 - P_r)P_r^{i-1}}{1 - P_r^N} \%, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (2)$$

Theoretically, P_r may vary between extreme values of 0 and 1. The extreme left value of P_r leads to a PSD in which all the aggregate particles are retained on the sieve with the largest opening size, thereby producing a trivial PSD. However, near the right extreme, it can be shown that

$$\lim_{P_r \rightarrow 1} P_i = \frac{100}{N} \%, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) implies that an equal mass of aggregate particles is retained on all sieves, producing a uniform distribution, with the PSD being a straight line in the log d % finer space. In this study (where $N = 8$), the extreme value of P_r led to each sieve retaining 12.50% of the entire aggregate mass. Hence, it can be concluded that a nontrivial aggregate distribution is generated when $0 \ll P_r < 1$. The implications of various P_r values on the PSD of the respective Carneiro distributions are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The effect of the P_r value on the PSD generated using Carneiro model.

4.3.2 The Dinger-Funk (D-F) model

The D-F model, a modified form of the Andreasen and Andreasen model [12], is a 3-parameter model used widely in the concrete industry to generate graded aggregate combinations. Instead of the percentage retained on each sieve, as in the Carneiro model, the D-F model provides the percentage passing each sieve for a prescribed D-F distribution modulus q , considering the opening diameters of the largest and smallest particle sizes. The D-F model is given by:

$$P_i = \frac{100(d^q - d_s^q)}{d_L^q - d_s^q} \% \quad (4)$$

Where P_i = the percent finer than a given particle size d

d_L = the largest particle size in the particulate system

d_s = the smallest particle size in the particulate system

q = D-F distribution modulus

Similar to the Carneiro model, the D-F distribution modulus q also has a theoretical value ranging between extreme values of 0 and 1. However, both extreme values produce non-trivial PSDs. Using the limit analysis, it can be shown that

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 0} P_i = \frac{\log d - \log d_s}{\log d_L - \log d_s}; \quad \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} P_i = \frac{d - d_s}{d_L - d_s} \quad (5)$$

Therefore, a near-left extreme value of q produces a linear PSD in $\log d$ % finer space, whereas the right extreme produces a nonlinear PSD in the same space. Interestingly, the same straight-

line PSD is produced with $P_r \rightarrow 1$ and $q \rightarrow 0$ for the Carneiro and D-F models, respectively. Hence, for the D-F model, it can be concluded that a nontrivial aggregate distribution can be generated with $0 < q \leq 1$. The impact of varying the values of q on the PSD of the respective D-F distributions is shown in Figure 3. A visual comparison of Figure 2 and Figure 3 shows that the D-F model is less sensitive to variations in its distribution modulus than is the Carneiro model.

Figure 3: The effect of the q value on the PSD generated through D-F model.

4.3.3 The Yamada and Miyauchi Model

As explained earlier, the aggregates considered in this work were idealized as spherical particles to obtain an idealized packing density of the individual aggregate size fraction (φ_i) of each size fraction. Therefore, to calculate the idealized value of φ_i for each aggregate size fraction, the formula proposed by Yamada and Miyauchi [31], subsequently referred to as the Y-M model, was used. The Y-M model suggests that φ_i of a particle system is a function of the measurement/packing container dimensions and the average particle size of the system, given by,

$$\varphi_i = \frac{0.604(V - 0.15S_A d_i)}{V} \quad (6)$$

where V = volume of the packing container (mm^3)

S_A = total surface area of the packing container (mm^2)

d_i = average spherical diameter of the i th size component (mm)

For the virtual cylindrical packing container considered in this study, V and S_A are given by

$$V = \frac{\pi D^2 h}{4}; \quad S_A = \frac{\pi D}{2} (D + 2h) \quad (7)$$

where H = height of the container

D = diameter of the container

4.4 The Compressible Packing Model

The CPM approach for determining the actual packing density of a polydisperse system of particles begins by calculating the residual packing density, β_i , defined as the maximum packing density that can be achieved by each monodisperse fraction in an infinite volume [10].

This parameter depends on the mean residual packing density, $\bar{\beta}_i$, which is the residual packing density affected by the wall effect of the container, and can be calculated, as suggested by De Larrad [10], as

$$\bar{\beta}_i = \left(1 + \frac{1}{K}\right) \varphi_i \quad (8)$$

where K = compaction index, a characteristic of the packing process

To obtain β_i , De Larrard [10] proposed Equation (9) which corrects $\bar{\beta}_i$ against the wall effect of the packing container as follows:

$$\beta_i = \frac{\bar{\beta}_i}{1 + (1 - k_w)[1 - (1 - d/D)^2(1 - d/h)]} \quad (9)$$

Where k_w = the wall effect coefficient;

$k_w = 0.88$ for round aggregate, and $k_w = 0.73$ for crushed aggregate

Using the value of β_i , the overall packing density (γ_i), defined as the maximum packing density the particle fraction can achieve in the mixture within the actual packing space, is then calculated using

$$\gamma_i = \frac{\beta_i}{1 - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \left[1 - \beta_i + b_{ij}\beta_i \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta_j}\right)\right] y_j - \sum_{j=i+1}^n \left[1 - a_{ij} \frac{\beta_i}{\beta_j}\right] y_j} \quad (10)$$

where a = the loosening effect coefficient of the size fraction

b = the wall effect coefficient of the size fraction

The loosening effect coefficient a was developed to capture the phenomenon whereby the introduction of small particles forces larger particles apart and can be calculated by

$$a_{ij} = \sqrt{1 - \left(1 - \frac{d_j}{d_i}\right)^{1.02}} \quad (11)$$

The wall effect coefficient b captures the phenomenon whereby larger particles create interstitials that are too small to be filled by other particle size classes in the mixture, and can be calculated by

$$b_{ji} = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{d_i}{d_j}\right)^{1.5} \quad (12)$$

Using the values of γ_i , the actual packing density ϕ of the aggregate mixture can be calculated implicitly by solving for ϕ in

$$K = \sum_{i=1}^n k_i = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\frac{y_i}{\beta_i}}{\frac{1}{\phi} - \frac{1}{\gamma_i}} \quad (13)$$

where K is the compaction index of the mixture, which is equal to the summation of the compaction indices k_i of individual size fractions. For dry packing processes with increasing packing energy input, De Larrad [10] proposed K values of 4.1, 4.5, 4.75, and 9 for pouring, rodding, vibration only, and vibration, respectively, under a compaction pressure of 10 kPa. For wet packing, a value of $K = 6.7$ was suggested. In this study, a value of 4.1 was selected for K , assuming pouring.

Finally, the segregation potential S for each aggregate mixture can be calculated using:

$$S = 1 - \min_{1 \leq i \leq n} \frac{k_i}{1 + k_i} \quad (14)$$

5 IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY

5.1 Generation of Analytical Aggregate Mixtures

To generate various experimental mixtures of aggregates conforming to a set of Carneiro and D-F distribution moduli, each of the four aggregates was represented as a percentage of the entire combination in the aggregate mixture. For a given size fraction of the aggregate, the percentage is given by:

$$y_i = c(PC1)_i + d(PC2)_i + e(PF1)_i + f(PF2)_i \quad (15)$$

Where y_i = size cumulative distribution function of the i th size

$PC1_i, PC2_i, PF1_i,$ and $PF2_i$ = passing fraction of the i th size of each aggregate class

c, d, e, f = variables representing the respective fractions of individual aggregate classes

Consequently, to determine the percentage of each of the four aggregates in the aggregate mixture with a PSD close enough to the target PSD obtained from the distribution model, the linear regression approach of minimizing the sum square of residuals (S_r) was employed. This approach is shown in (16).

$$S_r = \sum_{i=1}^n e_i^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n [P_i - y_i]^2 \quad (16)$$

Where P_i = size cumulative distribution obtained from each distribution model

e_i = residual for the i th size fraction between aggregate PSDs and calculated distributions

Using any optimization tool, S_r can be minimized mathematically or programmatically to determine a set of values of $c, d, e,$ and f that results in the lowest possible value of S_r .

It is worth highlighting that arrays P_i and y_i are essentially equivalent except that the former represents the ideal values obtained from an aggregate distribution model, whereas the latter constitutes the trained practical equivalent that can be achieved by combining individual aggregate classes utilizing the training weights c to f , which represent the respective combination fractions that add up to unity.

Obviously, achieving a 'perfect' fit, in which arrays P_i and y_i are exactly equal ($S_r = 0$), requires an impractically large number of aggregate classes. Therefore, while array y_i is required in

practical concrete (or any similar) applications, array P_i was employed in this study to model the relationship between the aggregate distribution moduli, the resultant packing density, and the corresponding segregation potential. On the other hand, the fitted aggregate combination fractions c to f were utilized to study the influence of the variation of each distribution moduli on the characteristics of the respective aggregate mixture.

5.2 Preliminary Packing Density Analyses

To select the analytical range to capture the maximum possible ϕ for each distribution model, the values of ϕ for P_r and q , presented in Figure 2 and Figure 3 were determined using the systematic procedures presented earlier. The preliminary results are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Preliminary values of ϕ over the entire domain of P_r and q .

As can be seen in Figure 4, the maximum ϕ is expected in the range $0.75 \leq P_r < 1$ for the Carneiro model, and in the range $0.05 \leq q < 0.25$ for the D-F model. Thus, these moduli ranges were investigated in the search for the optimum moduli values characterized by maximum or near-maximum packing densities ϕ and minimum or near-minimum segregation potentials S for the aggregate classes adopted in this study. Within the identified distribution moduli ranges, various values of ϕ and S were obtained using the procedures highlighted in Sections 3 and 4, respectively. The entire computational workflow was implemented on the Wolfram Mathematica® 10/Wolfram Cloud platform with minor computations and analyses conducted using Microsoft Excel. The computer code developed for implementing the computational workflow, as presented in Section 4, has been published elsewhere [32].

6 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

6.1 Impact of Distribution Moduli on the Size Composition of Aggregate Mixture

As stated earlier, for the aggregates employed in this work, sieve opening sizes of 19 to 0.075 mm, P_r range of 0.75 to 0.98, and q range of 0.05 to 0.35 were considered for detailed investigation. Detailed analytical aggregate size parameters and corresponding distribution results are presented in Appendix I.

For each of the aggregate type, the variation of the percentage of each type for varying values of the Carneiro distribution modulus in the range $0.75 \leq P_r < 1$ is presented in Figure 5. The relationships depicted in Figure 5 shows the behavior of each specific aggregate type for attaining a given value of P_r . For coarse aggregates, the coarser aggregate (CA1) diminishes faster than the less coarse aggregate as P_r increases, whereas for fine aggregates, the finer aggregate (FA2) rapidly increases linearly, as the less fine aggregate exhibits a slow quadratic response.

Figure 5: Variation of P_r with aggregate percentages

As in the case of the Carneiro model, for each of the aggregate types, the variation of the percentage of each type for varying values of the D-F distribution modulus in the range $0.05 \leq q < 0.25$ is presented in Figure 6. As expected, based on the trend noted in Figure 2 and Figure 3, the effects of varying q in the D-F model are exactly opposite to those of varying P_r in the Carneiro model, both in the general outlook and in the behavior of each specific aggregate type towards attaining a given value of q .

Figure 6: Variation of q with aggregate percentages.

6.2 Impact of Distribution Moduli on the Packing Density and Segregation Potential

By adopting the same ranges of distribution moduli, a detailed study was conducted to understand the influence of varying the distribution moduli on the packing density ϕ and segregation potential S to obtain the optimum distribution modulus for each model. By taking the mean size d_i of an aggregate particle as the simple average of any two consecutive sieve opening sizes, the value of φ_i for each mean particle size was calculated using Equation (6), in line with the previously detailed procedures. Using array φ_i , array $\bar{\beta}_i$ was obtained using Equation (8) and then corrected to β_i using Equation (9). Table 1 summarizes the values of φ_i , $\bar{\beta}_i$, and β_i for each mean particle size.

Table 1: φ_i , $\bar{\beta}_i$, and β_i for each mean size.

d	φ_i	$\bar{\beta}_i$	β_i
19-9.5	0.56493	0.70271	0.72004
9.5-4.75	0.58935	0.73309	0.74008
4.75-2.36	0.59669	0.74222	0.74579
2.36-1.18	0.60036	0.74679	0.74858
1.18-0.6	0.60217	0.74904	0.74995
0.6-0.3	0.60307	0.75017	0.75063
0.3-0.15	0.60354	0.75074	0.75097
0.15-0.075	0.60377	0.75103	0.75114

Using the values of β_i presented in Table 1, the CPM parameters a and b obtained through Equations (11) and (12), respectively, and the arrays P_i obtained through Equation (2), the values of the actual packing density ϕ and segregation potential S for each mixture were computed using Equations (13) and (14), respectively. As stated earlier, a compaction index $K = 4.1$ (pouring) was adopted in all computations. For the Carneiro model, the trends of ϕ and S as P_r increased are presented in Figure 7, highlighting the optimum P_r , considered as that corresponding to the maximum or near-maximum ϕ and minimum or near-minimum S . As can be observed in Figure 7, the maximum ϕ and minimum S corresponds to $P_r = 0.88$ and 0.87 , respectively. Apparently, the optimal aggregate mixtures result in the range $0.85 \leq P_r \leq 0.90$ for the aggregate combination considered in this work.

Figure 7: Variation of ϕ and S with P_r .

For the case of the D-F model, following the same approach as for the Carneiro model, but with the arrays P_i obtained through equation (4), the trends of ϕ and S as q increases are presented in Figure 8. As can be noted in Figure 8, the maximum ϕ and minimum S correspond to $q = 0.175$ and 0.2 , respectively. Apparently, the optimal aggregate mixtures result in the range of $0.15 \leq q \leq 0.25$ for the same aggregate combination.

Figure 8: Variation of ϕ and S with q .

In both model cases, Figure 7 and Figure 8 show that while ϕ exhibits a quadratic response, S exhibits a bilinear response to changes in the respective distribution modulus, both with high degrees of correlation of $R^2 \approx 1.0$. In addition, the absolute maximum ϕ in both cases is 0.777, whereas the absolute minimum S is approximately 0.7.

6.3 General Outlook of the Distribution Models

A general outlook on the performance of the two aggregate distribution models is hereby presented, starting with the characteristic size composition of the aggregate mixture. A comparison between Figure 2 and Figure 3 and Figure 5 and Figure 6 that the two models are somewhat equivalent, apart from the fact that the aggregate mixture characteristics respond in opposite directions with respect to the values of the respective distribution modulus.

Nevertheless, as discussed earlier, the aggregate mixture characteristics were less responsive to variations in the distribution modulus in the D-F model. With respect to packing density, a similar note can be deduced from Figure 4 and in better detail through a comparative assessment of Figure 7 and Figure 8; that is, the packing densities of aggregate mixtures are less responsive to variations in the D-F modulus. These observations imply that the identified optimal range of q in the D-F modulus may be slightly exceeded on both sides without a significant impact on the packing quality of the resulting aggregate mixture. Interestingly, it then follows that the D-F model is more flexible and robust for obtaining an aggregate mixture composition with optimal packing characteristics.

Overall, the application of these distribution models has been shown to be a better approach for concrete applications in the search for an optimal mixture composition from a set of aggregate-size classes. This contrasts with the usual practice of obtaining a large number of randomly generated combination ratios for aggregate-size classes. Further physical laboratory experiments need to be conducted in future studies to through which the approach presented in this study can be built upon with a view to developing a generally accurate methodology involving the synergistic use of these grading models and the compressible packing model.

Finally, two important points are worth emphasizing in the present study. First, the identified optimal ranges of the distribution modulus for each of the Carneiro and Dinger-Funk models may not necessarily be universally applicable for all aggregate types; they are most likely valid for the number of aggregate size classes and the geometrical and size characteristics of each aggregate size class. Second, as stated in the previous sections, the array φ_i of each mean particle size must be obtained experimentally for practical applications. The approach adopted in this study, in which φ_i was calculated using Equation (6), nevertheless, is very helpful in highlighting the salient features of the studied distribution models as well as establishing a practical methodology for developing an optimal distribution modulus for a set of aggregate class sizes for any distribution model. For any chosen distribution model, once the distribution modulus for any set of aggregate classes is established, Equation (15) and the associated notes presented in Section 5.1 come handy to obtain the appropriate combination percentages of the available aggregate size classes. Finally, the approach introduced in this study can be applied to any other application involving granular particulate mixtures, where mixture stability or segregation resistance is of paramount importance in addition to packing density, as in concrete technology.

7 CONCLUSIONS

This work explored the synergistic use of the compressible packing model with the Carneiro and Dinger-Funk aggregate distribution models utilizing a combination of two coarse aggregates and two fine aggregates to introduce a practical methodology for obtaining optimal distribution moduli considering packing density and segregation resistance. Based on the results obtained, along with pertinent discussions, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. For a nontrivial aggregate distribution utilizing the Carneiro model, the distribution modulus P_r should be in the range $0 < P_r < 1$, whereas the Dinger-Funk distribution modulus q should be in the range $0 < q \leq 1$.
2. Increasing the value of P_r leads to increasing volumes of finer aggregate components of the aggregate mixture simultaneously with decreasing coarse aggregate components, thereby increasing the fineness of the mixture. An increase in the value of q exhibits the opposite effect of increasing the value of P_r .
3. In both models, the packing density exhibited quadratic responses to variations in the distribution moduli, whereas the segregation resistance exhibited bilinear responses, both with very high correlation coefficients.
4. For the aggregate combination adopted in this work, the optimal aggregate mixtures result in the range $0.85 \leq P_r \leq 0.90$ and $0.15 \leq q \leq 0.25$ for Carneiro and Dinger-Funk models, respectively, with the segregation potentials in the neighborhood of 0.7.
5. For both models, the absolute maximum packing in both cases was 0.777 with negligible variations in the identified optimal distribution modulus ranges.
6. Although the Carneiro and Dinger-Funk distribution models appear to produce equivalent aggregate mixture characteristics, albeit in different directions of moduli changes, the latter is less responsive to changes in the distribution modulus.
7. It follows from the above that the Dinger-Funk model is somewhat more flexible and robust for obtaining an aggregate mixture composition with optimal packing characteristics.
8. The approach introduced in this study is applicable to any application involving granular particulate mixtures, where a high packing density and mixture stability are desired.

8 REFERENCES

- [1] B.M. Aïssoun, S.-D. Hwang, K.H. Khayat, Influence of aggregate characteristics on workability of superworkable concrete, *Mater. Struct. Constr.* 49 (2016) 597–609. <https://doi.org/10.1617/s11527-015-0522-9>.
- [2] X. Chateau, *Particle packing and the rheology of concrete*, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-85709-028-7.50006-6>.
- [3] M. Reisi, D. Mostofinejad, A.A. Ramezani pour, Computer simulation-based method to predict packing density of aggregates mixture, *Adv. Powder Technol.* 29 (2018) 386–398. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APT.2017.11.026>.
- [4] J.J. Chen, G.X. Guan, P.L. Ng, A.K.H. Kwan, S.H. Chu, Packing optimization of paste and aggregate phases for sustainability and performance improvement of concrete, *Adv. Powder Technol.* 32 (2021) 987–997. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APT.2021.02.008>.
- [5] C.S. Karadumpa, R.K. Pancharathi, Developing a novel mix design methodology for slow hardening composite cement concretes through packing density approach, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 303 (2021) 124391. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CONBUILDMAT.2021.124391>.
- [6] M.H. Mohammed, M. Emborg, R. Pusch, S. Knutsson, Packing theory for natural and crushed aggregate to obtain the best mix of aggregate: Research and development, in: *Proc. WASET Int. Conf. Civ. Constr. Eng. Stock. Sweden*, 2012: pp. 819–825.
- [7] H.H.C. Wong, A.K.H. Kwan, Packing density: a key concept for mix design of high performance concrete, in: *Proc. Mater. Sci. Technol. Eng. Conf. HKIE Mater. Div. Hong Kong*, Citeseer, 2005: pp. 1–15.
- [8] S. Ahmad, M. Maslehuddin, M. Shameem, R. Md Faysal, S. Kolawole Adekunle, *European Journal of Environmental and Civil Engineering* Effect of abrasion and chemical treatment of recycled aggregate on the workability, strength, and durability properties of concrete Effect of abrasion and chemical treatment of recycled aggregate on the workability, strength, and durability properties of concrete, (n.d.). <https://doi.org/10.1080/19648189.2020.1797886>.
- [9] S.H. Chu, C.S. Poon, C.S. Lam, L. Li, Effect of natural and recycled aggregate

- packing on properties of concrete blocks, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 278 (2021) 122247. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2021.122247>.
- [10] F. de Larrard, *Concrete mixture proportioning: A scientific approach*, 1st ed., CRC Press, London, 1999. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/mono/10.1201/9781482272055/concrete-mixture-proportioning-francois-de-larrard>.
- [11] The effect of aggregate packing on the performance of SCC using dune sand, in: *Proc. Fifth North Am. Conf. Des. Use Self-Consolidating Concr.*, Chicago, USA, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.5171.4081>.
- [12] J.E. Funk, D.R. Dinger, *Predictive Process Control of Crowded Particulate Suspensions*, 1st ed., Springer US, 1994. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4615-3118-0>.
- [13] S. Fennis, J. Walraven, Using particle packing technology for sustainable concrete mixture design, *Heron*. 57 (2012) 73–101.
- [14] G. Yuan, P. Hao, D. Li, J. Pan, S. Dong, Optimization design and verification of Large Stone Porous asphalt Mixes gradation using Compressible Packing Model, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 230 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.116903>.
- [15] T. Baghaee Moghaddam, H. Baaj, Application of compressible packing model for optimization of asphalt concrete mix design, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 159 (2018) 530–539. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2017.11.004>.
- [16] A.K.H. Kwan, K.W. Chan, V. Wong, A 3-parameter particle packing model incorporating the wedging effect, *Powder Technol.* 237 (2013) 172–179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2013.01.043>.
- [17] N.A. Soliman, A. Tagnit-Hamou, Using particle packing and statistical approach to optimize eco-efficient ultra-high-performance concrete, *ACI Mater. J.* 114 (2017) 847–858. <https://doi.org/10.14359/51701001>.
- [18] A. Arora, A. Almujaiddi, F. Kianmofrad, B. Mobasher, N. Neithalath, Material design of economical ultra-high performance concrete (UHPC) and evaluation of their properties, *Cem. Concr. Compos.* 104 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2019.103346>.

- [19] ASTM International, ASTM C33/C33M – 18: Standard Specification for Concrete Aggregates, in: Annu. B. ASTM Stand., ASTM International, 100 Barr Harbor Drive, PO Box C700, West Conshohocken, PA, 19428-2959 USA, 2018.
- [20] H.A.C.K. Hettiarachchi, W.K. Mamppearachchi, Validity of aggregate packing models in mixture design of interlocking concrete block pavers (ICBP), *Road Mater. Pavement Des.* 20 (2019) 462–474. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14680629.2017.1393001>.
- [21] N. Sebaibi, M. Benzerzour, Y. Sebaibi, N.-E. Abriak, Composition of self compacting concrete (SCC) using the compressible packing model, the Chinese method and the European standard, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 43 (2013) 382–388. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2013.02.028>.
- [22] J. Van Der Putten, J. Dils, P. Minne, V. Boel, G. De Schutter, Determination of packing profiles for the verification of the compressible packing model in case of UHPC pastes, *Mater. Struct. Constr.* 50 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1617/s11527-016-0986-2>.
- [23] M. Bala, R. Zentar, P. Boustingorry, Parameter determination of the Compressible Packing Model (CPM) for concrete application, *Powder Technol.* 367 (2020) 56–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2019.11.085>.
- [24] Carneiro Arnaldo Manoel Pereira, Contribution to the study of the aggregate effect on the properties of mortars composed from grading curves, São Paulo, Brazil, 1999.
- [25] K.A. Melo, A.M.P. Carneiro, Effect of Metakaolin’s finesses and content in self-consolidating concrete, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 24 (2010) 1529–1535. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2010.02.002>.
- [26] G. Hüsken, H.J.H. Brouwers, A new mix design concept for earth-moist concrete: A theoretical and experimental study, *Cem. Concr. Res.* 38 (2008) 1246–1259. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2008.04.002>.
- [27] M. Hunger, An integral design concept for ecological self-compacting concrete, Eindhoven University of Technology, 2010.
- [28] H.J.H. Brouwers, Particle-size distribution and packing fraction of geometric random packings, *Phys. Rev. E.* 74 (2006) 031309. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.74.031309>.

- [29] Q.L. Yu, P. Spiesz, H.J.H. Brouwers, Development of cement-based lightweight composites - Part 1: Mix design methodology and hardened properties, *Cem. Concr. Compos.* 44 (2013) 17–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2013.03.030>.
- [30] R. Yu, P. Spiesz, H.J.H. Brouwers, Effect of nano-silica on the hydration and microstructure development of Ultra-High Performance Concrete (UHPC) with a low binder amount, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 65 (2014) 140–150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2014.04.063>.
- [31] S. Yamada, J. Kanno, M. Miyauchi, *Multi-sized sphere packing*, 2009.
- [32] A.A. Abdulkader, S.K. Adekunle, A Mathematica Code for the Computation of Packing Density and Segregation Potential for Multi-sized Aggregates using Compressible Packing Model through Carneiro and Dinger-Funk Models, (2022). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5078531>.

APPENDIX I

The sieve analysis obtained from the laboratory for the four types of aggregates adopted in this work, as well as the best-fitted percentages of each type for varying values of the distribution moduli, are presented here.

Table AI-1: Sieve analysis of coarse aggregate.

Sieve opening (mm)	CA1 (19 mm) *			CA2 (9.5 mm) **		
	Retained %	Cumulative %	Passing %	Retained %	Cumulative %	Passing %
19	0	0	100	0	0	100
12.5	42.4	42.4	57.6	0	0	100
9.5	37.7	80.1	19.9	0.2	0.2	99.8
4.75	18.9	99	1	69.6	69.8	30.2
2.36	1	100	0	28.7	98.5	1.5
1.18	0	100	0	1.5	100	0
0.6	0	100	0	0	100	0
0.3	0	100	0	0	100	0
0.15	0	100	0	0	100	0
0.075	0	100	0	0	100	0

*CA1 = Coarse aggregate 1 with a maximum aggregate size of 19 mm.

**CA2 = Coarse aggregate 2 having a maximum aggregate size of 9.5 mm

Table AI-2: Sieve analysis of fine aggregate.

Sieve opening (mm)	FA1 (4.75 mm)*			FA2 (0.6 mm)**		
	Retained %	Cumulative %	Passing %	Retained %	Cumulative %	Passing %
19	0	0	100	0	0	100
12.5	0	0	100	0	0	100
9.5	0	0	100	0	0	100
4.75	7.2	7.2	92.8	0	0	100
2.36	57.6	64.8	35.2	0	0	100
1.18	26.4	91.2	8.8	0	0	100
0.6	2.8	94	6	4.8	4.8	95.2
0.3	2.5	96.5	3.5	34.8	39.6	60.4
0.15	1.5	98	2	39.5	79.1	20.9
0.075	2	100	0	20.9	100	0

*FA1 = Fine aggregate 1 with maximum aggregate size of 4.75 mm

**FA2 = Fine aggregate 2 having a maximum aggregate size of 0.6 mm

Table AI-3: Best-fitted percentages of each aggregate type for values of P_r (Carneiro).

P_r	CA1	CA2	FA1	FA2	CA*	FA*
0.75	35.73	11.65	34.45	18.17	47.38	52.62
0.76	34.78	11.33	34.83	19.06	46.11	53.89
0.77	33.85	11.00	35.19	19.96	44.85	55.15
0.78	32.93	10.66	35.51	20.89	43.60	56.40
0.79	32.03	10.33	35.81	21.83	42.36	57.64
0.80	31.15	9.99	36.08	22.79	41.13	58.87
0.81	30.27	9.65	36.32	23.76	39.92	60.08
0.82	29.42	9.31	36.52	24.75	38.73	61.27
0.83	28.58	8.96	36.70	25.75	37.55	62.45
0.84	27.76	8.62	36.86	26.76	36.38	63.62
0.85	26.95	8.29	36.98	27.78	35.24	64.76
0.86	26.16	7.95	37.07	28.82	34.11	65.89
0.87	25.39	7.62	37.13	29.86	33.01	66.99
0.88	24.64	7.29	37.17	30.91	31.92	68.08
0.89	23.90	6.96	37.18	31.96	30.86	69.14
0.90	23.18	6.64	37.16	33.03	29.81	70.19
0.91	22.47	6.32	37.11	34.09	28.79	71.21
0.92	21.78	6.01	37.04	35.16	27.80	72.20
0.93	21.11	5.71	36.94	36.24	26.82	73.18
0.94	20.45	5.41	36.82	37.31	25.87	74.13
0.95	19.82	5.12	36.67	38.39	24.94	75.06
0.96	19.19	4.84	36.50	39.46	24.04	75.96
0.97	18.59	4.57	36.31	40.54	23.15	76.85
0.98	18.00	4.30	36.09	41.61	22.30	77.70
0.99	17.42	4.04	35.86	42.68	21.46	78.54
1.00	16.86	3.79	35.60	43.74	20.66	79.34

*CA = Effective percentage of coarse aggregate considering size fractions of 5 mm and below as the fine aggregate fraction of the aggregate mixture.

**FA = Effective percentage of fine aggregate based on the above consideration

Note that the values for CA1, CA2, FA1, and FA2 here correspond to c , d , f , and e of Equation (15) for each case, but are expressed as percentages.

Table AI-4: Best-fitted percentages of each aggregate type for values of q (D-F).

q	CA1	CA2	FA1	FA2	CA	FA
0.050	18.84	4.82	36.31	40.04	23.65	76.35
0.075	19.86	5.28	36.60	38.26	25.14	74.86
0.100	20.92	5.76	36.82	36.51	26.67	73.33
0.125	21.99	6.24	36.98	34.79	28.23	71.77
0.150	23.09	6.73	37.07	33.11	29.83	70.17
0.175	24.21	7.23	37.09	31.47	31.44	68.56
0.200	25.35	7.73	37.05	29.87	33.08	66.92
0.225	26.51	8.23	36.95	28.31	34.74	65.26
0.250	27.69	8.72	36.78	26.81	36.41	63.59
0.275	28.88	9.22	36.56	25.35	38.09	61.91
0.300	30.08	9.70	36.28	23.94	39.78	60.22
0.325	31.29	10.17	35.95	22.59	41.47	58.54
0.350	32.52	10.63	35.57	21.28	43.15	56.85

*CA = Effective percentage of coarse aggregate considering size fractions of 5 mm and below as the fine aggregate fraction of the aggregate mixture.

**FA = Effective percentage of fine aggregate based on the above consideration

Note that the values for CA1, CA2, FA1, and FA2 here correspond to c , d , f , and e of Equation (15) for each case but are expressed as percentages.